

Start on Sustainability Starter Kit

7. SUPPLY CHAIN TRANSPARENCY

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A photograph of a modern building with a curved facade and a large tree in the foreground. The building has a white, curved wall and a grid of windows. The tree is green and leafy. The image is partially obscured by a blue overlay on the right side.

ABOUT OUR PROJECT

By implementing Start on Sustainability, we aim **to equip micro-enterprises** with the necessary **tools and resources** to take meaningful action towards sustainability, thereby contributing to a more sustainable and resilient EU economy.

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01

INTRODUCTION TO THE MODULE

01

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1. OVERVIEW

- Achieving the goals and objectives on sustainability directly implies the involvement of all stakeholders which, indeed, can be ensured by “cascade procedures” in value and supply chains in the economy.
- Improving transparency across supply chains can contribute to ensure ethical and sustainable sourcing practices across value chains.
- Even though reporting on non-financial information in sustainable goals and procedures are not mandatory for micro-enterprises at present, obligations might indirectly affect them if they’re involved in supply chains with larger companies that are obliged to comply with regulatory requirements.
- In this unit we will analyse which are the obligations established by EU Directives for large companies and how they can affect micro-enterprises that are part of their supply chains.
- We will also assess on how to be prepared for obliged larger partners requirements and avoid “market expulsion effects” if we do not comply with them.

02. OBJECTIVES

This Unit aims to reach a better understanding about the obligations related to transparency and impact and risks evaluations that micro-enterprises might have to face if they're part of a supply chain or value chain involving larger actors

Specific objectives

- Analyse the European regulatory framework affecting supply and value chains - Mainly two Directives: CSRD and CSDDD.
- Identify the companies that are obliged to fulfil responsibilities concerning supply and value chains.
- Understand the direct obligations of larger companies and indirect obligations in sustainability and the requirements that micro-enterprises could face when they're part of their supply chain or value chain.

03. LEARNING OUTCOMES

- What is considered as a supply or value chain and a “cascade procedure”?
- Which companies are obliged by European regulatory mandates on reporting information of their supply chain or value chain and how it can affect micro-enterprises?
- Which information do they require to be prepared?
- What are the advantages of transparency in supply chains?

02

**REGULATORY OBLIGATIONS ON
SUSTAINABILITY IN SUPPLY AND VALUE
CHAINS**

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01. Supply chain and value chain

definitions

- **Supply chains** is related mainly to products: involves the movement of components and finished products from suppliers to manufacturers, distributors, retailers and ultimately to end users.
- While the definition of value chains has a broader scope: it not only includes the production and distribution of goods but also the provision of services and all the related activities of every partner involved in their upstream and downstream established business relations (contractors, subcontractors, other legal entities and the employment of all of them)

02. Regulatory framework on sustainable supply chain and value chain in the EU

Two types of EU regulation:

- **Affecting the product (supply chain):** use of raw materials, traceability of the product, (initiative of EC of PRODUCT DIGITAL PASSPORT), etc.
- **Affecting all** the established (in view of the intensity or duration) direct or indirect **business relationships of a company (value chain):** including employment or financing services

Supply chain is included in the value chain but generally has a more focused sectorial view or obligations regarding an specific product

2.1. Supply and value chain EU regulations

Green Deal Stocktake: delivering on law-making

EU Climate Law
2030 Climate Target
EU Emissions Trading System
Just Transition Fund
Social Climate Fund
Effort Sharing Regulation
Land Use, Forestry and Agriculture
CO2 emissions standards cars and vans
Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism
Adaptation Strategy
Methane emissions
Industrial emissions
Carbon Removals
Net-Zero Industry Act
Green Deal Industrial Plan
2040 climate target

Renewable Energy Directive
Energy Efficiency Directive
Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EU Methane Regulation
RePowerEU
Electricity Market Design
Gas markets and hydrogen
Energy price emergency measures
Energy Labelling
Fluorinated Gases

Circular Economy Action Plan
European Industrial Strategy
8th Environmental Action Programme
EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030
Critical Raw Materials Act
Net-Zero Industry Act
Chemicals strategy for sustainability
Zero pollution Action Plan
Deforestation
Waste shipments
Soil Monitoring
Ecodesign for Sustainable Products
Empowering Consumers Green Transition
Construction Products
Sustainable Textiles Strategy
Nature Restoration
Waste Framework
Right to Repair
Green Claims
Pesticides
Air Quality
Urban wastewater
Packaging and Packaging Waste
Critical Raw Materials Act
Forest monitoring
Classification and labeling of Chemicals
REACH

2.2 Value chain EU regulation on sustainability: CSRD and CSDDD

1) CSRD: Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive:

- Requires companies, both large and small, to report on their environmental and social impact activities and defines for the first time a common reporting framework for non-financial data. Ultimately, it helps stakeholders (including investors) assess the non-financial performance of organisations. In the long term, it aims to encourage companies within its scope to develop more responsible approaches to business conduct.
- Mandates companies to disclose information not just about their own activities but also about their upstream and downstream value chain, including their products, services, and business relationships.
- This expansive view demands a nuanced understanding of the value chain, as delineated in the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) Delegated Act, challenging companies to identify, address, and report on sustainability impacts in a way that aligns with international due diligence standards.

2.3 Value chain EU regulation on sustainability: CSRD and CSDD

2) CSDDD or CS3D: Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive

- Due diligence is a process that allows companies to identify, prevent, mitigate, and account for how to address their actual and potential adverse impacts and it extends to all of parts involved in the value chain
- It means acceptance of the code of conduct established by the obliged partner by EU legislation and standards, measuring the adverse impacts of our activities and delivering an action plan to mitigate, neutralize or minimise their extent.

Conclusion: CSDR is about reporting on sustainability data and evaluating risks on a standardized form (INFO), and CS3D due diligence (ACTION) involves accepting a code of conduct, recognising our adverse effects as companies on human rights and environmental impacts, and developing a plan to mitigate them

2.4 Who's obliged

CSRD:

The CSRD applies to all large companies established in an EU Member State or governed by EU law, These companies would include both SMEs and large public-interest entities.

It also applies to all European companies listed on the stock exchange (except micro-enterprises) and to global companies that have operations (subject to thresholds)/securities listed on a regulated market in Europe.

The directive defines a large company as one that meets at least two of the following three criteria

- **€40 million in net turnover;**
- **€20 million of total assets on the balance sheet;**
- **250 or more employees.**

2.5 Who's obliged

The CSDDD Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive regulates the responsibilities of companies for potential adverse impacts on human rights and the environment.

-> This includes its own operations, those of its subsidiaries and those carried out by companies within its chain of activities (supply, production and distribution).

-> In addition, it addresses liability in the event of non-compliance with these obligations.

-> Finally, it requires companies to adopt and implement a transition plan to reduce or mitigate the effects of climate change.

2.6 Who's obliged

CSDDD applies to the following companies:

1. Companies incorporated in the EU and also working with third countries which have:

- more than 500 employees on an average
- a worldwide net turnover of more than EUR 150 million in the last financial year

2. Risk sectors: companies that do not reach those thresholds but have more of 250 employees on average and a worldwide net turnover of 40 million in the last financial year, provided that at least 50% of its net worldwide turnover was generated in one of more of the following :

- The manufacture of textiles, leather and related products (including footwear) and the wholesale trade of textiles, clothing and footwear
- agriculture, forestry, fisheries (including aquaculture), the manufacture of food products, and the wholesale trade of agricultural raw materials, live animals, wood, food and beverages
- the extraction of mineral resources regardless from where they are extracted; the manufacture of basic metal products (except machinery and equipment) and the wholesale trade of mineral resources - basic and intermediate mineral products.

02.7 Who's obliged?

3. The Directive shall also apply to **companies which are formed in accordance with the legislation of a third country**, and fulfil one of the following conditions:

- generated a net turnover of more than 150 million of euros in the Union in the financial year preceding the last financial year.
- generated a net turnover of more than 40 million but not more than 150 million in the Union in the financial year preceding the last financial year, provided that at least 50% of its net worldwide turnover was generated in one or more of the “risk sectors” listed before.

3.1 Main regulatory direct and indirect obligations for micro-enterprises in supply and value chains

CSRD:

- **Report for the 2024 reporting from 2025** to companies with more than 500 employees, which are subject to the 2014 Non-Financial Reporting Directive
- Report for the 2025 financial year from 2026** to companies with more than 250 employees and/or a turnover of 40 million euros and/or 20 million euros in total assets
- Report for the 2026 financial year from 2027** for listed SMEs, credit institutions and small insurers
- From 2028**, the CSRD will apply to all other SMEs for the 2027 financial year, **except for micro-SMEs**

3.2 Main regulatory direct and indirect obligations for micro-enterprises in supply and value chains

It is important to highlight **the connection between the CS3D Directive and the CSRD Directive**, especially with regard to corporate sustainability reporting.

For example, in order to produce the sustainability reporting required by the CSRD Directive, processes that are linked to the identification of the negative impacts of the CSDDD Directive will be required.

- ❓ **So even if there are no direct obligations regarding micro companies, there are indirect obligations related to being connected or integrated in a value or supply chain**
- ❓ **CASCADE EFFECTS: micro companies involved in value or supply chains will be required to supply data to obliged actors of the chain adopt their code of conduct related to sustainability and due diligence (CS3D)**

3.3 Main regulatory direct and indirect obligations for micro-enterprises in supply and value chains

CSDDD: This regulation will be gradually applied to EU companies (and to non-EU companies that meet the same turnover thresholds in the EU):

-> In 2027, to EU companies with 5,000 employees and a net worldwide turnover exceeding €1,500M, and to non-EU companies that meet this turnover threshold in the European market.

-> In 2028, to EU companies with more than 3,000 employees and a net worldwide turnover exceeding €900M, and to non-EU companies with the same turnover threshold in the European market.

-> In 2029, to other companies subject to the Directive.

3.3 Main regulatory direct and indirect obligations for micro-enterprises in supply and value chains

- A number of injunctions are included for companies that fail to pay fines imposed in the event of infringement.

-> Additionally the company's turnover is taken into account to impose financial penalties (i.e. a **maximum minimum of 5% of the company's net turnover**).

- And companies will be obliged to make a meaningful commitment, including dialogue and consultation with affected stakeholders.

-> In addition, **the agreement establishes that compliance with the CSDDD could be qualified as a criterion for the award of public contracts and concessions.**

4. First step: Transparency

To be prepared to respond for indirect obligations as a Micro company involved in a value or supply chain, they should:

- Identify activity risks and impacts for environment and human rights
- Organise the information in a standardised (EGS) and transparent way
- Elaborate a Plan of Action

The CSDDD indicates that accessible and practical support is necessary for SMEs in the value chain to prepare for the obligations and the consequent demands that may be passed on to them indirectly. This could include practical guidance and supporting tools such as hotlines, database or training, as well as an observatory to help companies with the implementation of the Directive. Additionally, companies subject to the Directive are obliged to give support and provide tools to SMEs in their value chain.

4.1 First step: Transparency

Starting in corporate data transparency on sustainability is the first step to avoid **market expulsion effect** in the mid long term:

1. If micro-sme's are not prepared, they could lose clients that have to comply with sustainability regulation
2. They could also face future restrictions on financing or not accessing green financing tools
3. Additionally, they could not be beneficiaries of public aids, funds and public procurement.

“We care about every worker in our worldwide supply chain..what we will not do –and never have done- is stand still or turn a blind eye to problems in our supply chain. On this you have my word”

Tim Cook (Apple)

03

CASE STUDIES

01

Case study 1: ECOEMBES

02

**Case study 2: CONSTRUCTION SECTOR IN SPAIN
AND ENERGY EFFICIENCY**

03

Case study 3: IMPACT HUB

Case study 1: ECOEMBES

Ecoembes, is a spanish well-known environmental non-profit organisation, that carries out the recycling and eco-design of packaging in Spain, and has several programs for supporting SMEs through guides and training.

In its **VIII Business Prevention Plan (2021-2023)**, it highlights that 62% of all professional SME projects are already aware of the need to limit the environmental impact of their activities. They are moving towards a circular economy by focusing on both recycling packaging and improving packaging design to enhance recyclability

The most frequent decisions regarding a greener design of their companies' packaging revolve around the idea of improving the recyclability of such packaging, and that the recycled material is also incorporated into the manufacturing phase.

However, progress is still needed on other equally important ethical and ecological issues, such as reducing the weight of packaging for all types of products and optimizing space to minimize packaging. Additionally, using materials that have a lower environmental impact from the outset is crucial. More radical measures, such as bulk purchasing and the use of reusable packaging, are also becoming more common.

The movement among SMEs in Spain toward using less polluting packaging has been significant, yielding impressive results. Over 2,000 Spanish SMEs have adopted these practices, leading to substantial achievements. According to the report, more than 60,000 tonnes of raw materials have been saved, over 4 billion containers have been improved, and nearly 1 million tonnes of CO2 emissions have been avoided.

Case study 2: PEFC SPAIN

PEFC Spain is a non-profit, non-governmental organisation that promotes and disseminates Sustainable Forest Management, through forest certification and the chain of custody of forest products.

This contributes to environmental and biodiversity conservation and promotes the social economy, circularity and sustainable development.

PEFC provides foresters, forest owners and managers, from small to large property, with a tool to demonstrate their responsible practices, while helping consumers and businesses choose sustainably sourced forest products.

In this case study we will analyse the case of construction projects. The construction industry faces the challenge of proving that the wood supplied in the various projects comes from certified sustainable sources. **Chain of Custody certification is not always the most efficient option for these short-term projects involving different non-certified SME and micro-SME contractors.**

Many contractors of all sizes will be involved in the project and not all will have their own Chain of Custody certification, specially the smaller ones.

Project certification allows non-certified subcontractors to work under the "umbrella" of prime contractor certification, as long as all of their activities are limited to the certified project.

The certification of the wood or its derived products used in the project provides an independent guarantee that it comes from sustainably managed forests, **ensuring traceability through each stage of the production process, from the forest to the final project.**

This type of certification makes visible the organisation's commitment to the sustainable management of forests, in line with the 2030 Sustainable Development Goals and the fight against climate change.

Medicamento y Medio Ambiente

Case study 3: SIGRE

SIGRE is a Spanish non-profit organisation in charge of guaranteeing the correct environmental management of the packaging and remains of medicines that are generated in homes.

Launched in 2001 as a result of collaboration between the pharmaceutical industry, pharmacies, and pharmaceutical distribution companies, this initiative aims to be an effective and efficient model

One of its greatest achievements has been to involve the entire value chain of the medicine, especially the pharmacy network in the project. 100% of pharmacies in Spain are micro-SMEs.

SIGRE not only establishes the collection points for expired or leftover medicines at pharmacy points and organises their collection, but also trains pharmacy professionals and offers consultancy on sustainability, eco-design and traceability of medicines in order to prevent them from becoming non-recyclable waste.

Such drugs are extremely harmful to the environment. Additionally, they are able to affect the entire food chain through wildlife and generate serious public health problems.

“We don’t have to engage in grand, heroic actions to participate in change. Small acts, when multiplied by million of people, can transform the world.”

Howard Zinn, expert in city planning, a builder and a land-use consultant who represented part of the San Fernando Valley on the Los Angeles City Council from 1981 until his death in 1986.

04

ASSESSMENT

Q1

What is the main difference between a 'supply chain' and a 'value chain'

- A. The supply chain focuses on the flow of products and materials, while the value chain emphasizes the creation of value at each step of the process.
- B. The supply chain is concerned with marketing strategies, whereas the value chain is concerned with logistics and distribution.
- C. The supply chain involves customer service and support, while the value chain only involves manufacturing processes.

Q2

What is the primary focus of the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)?

- A. Identifying and mitigating actual and potential adverse impacts in the value chain.
- B. Reporting on environmental and social impact activities using a standardized framework.
- C. Establishing a code of conduct for business activities.

Q3

How does the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CS3D) differ from the CSRD in terms of its main purpose?

- A. CS3D focuses on the acceptance of a code of conduct and action plans to address adverse impacts, while CSRD focuses on standardized reporting of sustainability data.
- B. CS3D requires reporting on environmental impact activities, whereas CSRD mandates due diligence in the value chain.
- C. CS3D is concerned with the disclosure of financial data, while CSRD addresses non-financial performance.

Q4

Which directive requires third-country companies to assess and mitigate their adverse impacts in the value chain?

- A. Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD)
- B. Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD)
- C. Both CSRD and CSDDD

Q5

According to the given text, what is true about the obligations of micro companies under the CS3D and CSRD Directives?

- A. Microcompanies have direct obligations under the CS3D Directive and must comply with all sustainability reporting requirements
- a) Microcompanies have no direct obligations, but they face indirect obligations by being part of a value or supply chain, such as providing data and adopting sustainability codes of conduct.
- b) Microcompanies are exempt from both direct and indirect obligations related to corporate sustainability and due diligence

Answer Key

Q1: A

Q2: B

Q3: A

Q4: A

Q5: A

“Sustainable development is a fundamental break that’s going to reshuffle the entire deck. There are companies today that are going to dominate in the future simply because they understand that.”

Francois-Henri Pinault, General Manager of France Bois Industries

05

KEY TERMS AND DEFINITIONS

-
- **Supply chains** is related mainly to products: involves the movement of components and finished products from suppliers to manufacturers, distributors, retailers and ultimately to end users.
 - While **value chains** definition has a larger extent: not only limits itself to the production and distribution of goods but also to the provision of services and all the related activities of every partner involved in their upstream and downstream established business relations (contractors, subcontractors, other legal entities and the employment of all of them)
 - **SME means a micro, small or a medium-sized enterprise**, irrespective of its legal form that have less than 250 employees
 - **Micro-smes or micro companies:** companies of less than 10 employees.

-
- **Adverse environmental impact:** means an adverse impact on the environment resulting from the violation of one of the prohibitions and obligations pursuant to international environmental conventions.
 - **Adverse human rights impact:** means an adverse impact on protected persons resulting from the violation of one of the rights or prohibitions in international conventions and declarations.
 - **Business relationship** means a relationship with a contractor, subcontractor or any other legal entities (partners):
 - with whom the company has a commercial agreement or to whom the company provides financing, insurance or reinsurance or.
 - that performs business operations related to the products or services of the company on the behalf of the company

- **Established business relationship** means a business relationship, whether direct or indirect, which is expected to be lasting, in view of the intensity or duration and which does not represent a negligible or merely ancillary part of the value chain.
- **Subsidiary:** means a legal person through which the activity of a controlled undertaking is exercised.
- **Stakeholders:** means the company's employees, employees of its subsidiaries, and other individuals, groups communities or entities whose rights or interests are or could be defined by the products, services, and operations of that company, its subsidiaries and its business relationships.

“The greatest threat to our planet is the belief that someone else will save it.”

Robert Swan, World-Class Speaker and Polar Explorer.

06

REFERENCES

REFERENCES

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- Proposal for a DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence and amending Directive (EU) 2019/1937COM/2022/71 final.
- Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions — The European Green Deal (COM(2019) 640 final, 11.12.2019).
- SME United, Implementation of the Green Deal Next Steps, Andreas Brieger, Climate/Energy/Environment Policy Director.

Thank You
Any questions?

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